

SYMPTOMS AND TREATMENT OF THRUSH IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. Thrush is a fungal (yeast) infection that can grow in your mouth, throat and other parts of your body. With oral thrush (oral candidiasis), you may develop white, raised, cottage cheese-like lesions (spots) on your tongue and cheeks. Thrush can quickly become irritated and cause mouth pain and redness.

Key words: thrush, mouth, throat, body, tongue, infection, spots, pain, redness.

СИМПТОМЫ И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ МОЛЧОЧКИ У ДЕТЕ

Аннотация. Молочница – это грибковая инфекция, которая может расти во рту, горле и других частях тела. При молочнице (оральный кандидоз) у вас могут развиваться белые, поднятие, похожие на творог поражения (пятна) на языке и щеках. Молочница может быстро раздражаться и вызывать боль и покраснение во рту.

Ключевые слова: молочница, рот, горло, тело, язык, инфекция, пятна, боль, покраснение.

Thrush is a fungal infection of your mouth and throat. It is caused by an overgrowth of Candida yeast. Antibiotics and immune system problems can raise your risk of thrush. It is uncommon in people without underlying conditions.

Thrush is a mouth infection that is common in babies and children. Symptoms include white or yellow velvety patches in the mouth. Thrush is caused by a type of fungus called Candida. Candida is found naturally on the skin and in the mouth. But if Candida grows out of control, it can cause thrush.

Candida yeast is common in the everyday environment. It only causes a problem when it grows out of control. This can happen if a child:

- Has taken antibiotics
- Uses inhaled corticosteroids, such as for asthma
- Uses a pacifier often
- Has a weak immune system

If your child has oral thrush, you might notice that they have white spots and patches that look like cottage cheese on their tongue, inner cheeks, lips, gums or roof of their mouth. These patches don't rub off with gentle pressure. If the patches are removed, they leave inflamed areas that can bleed.

A child with oral thrush might also have cracking and inflammation at the corners of their mouth. They might not be able to taste things as well as usual.

Oral thrush generally doesn't irritate babies and young children. But it might cause irritation if the areas get very inflamed. In this case, your child might not want to feed or eat. They might also drool. And if the infection spreads to your child's food pipe, it can be painful and make it hard for them to swallow.

If a baby is breastfeeding, they can pass on thrush, which can cause a nipple infection. This kind of infection causes inflamed, sensitive and cracked nipples. Your breast might hurt during feeding, and you might have a stabbing pain deep in your breast.

Although oral thrush can affect anyone, it's more likely to occur in babies and older adults because they have reduced immunity; in other people with suppressed immune systems or certain health conditions; or people who take certain medications. Oral thrush is a minor problem if you're healthy, but if you have a weakened immune system, symptoms may be more severe and difficult to control.

Thrush is not a serious problem for a healthy child. It can be treated with antifungal medicine.

Your GP or Health Visitor may prescribe an antifungal treatment called Nystatin oral suspension if your baby is under 4 months. Older babies are usually prescribed Miconazole gel. Nystatin comes with a dropper that you can use to apply the medicine on the affected areas after feeds.

The healthcare provider will ask about your child's symptoms and health history. They will give your child a physical exam. This will include looking in your child's mouth.

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Treatment will depend on your child's symptoms, age, and general health. It will also depend on how bad the condition is.

A healthy baby with mild thrush may not need any treatment. More severe cases are likely to be treated with a liquid antifungal medicine. This is given through a dropper into your child's mouth. Or the medicine may be given as pills in an older child. Follow the healthcare provider's instructions for giving this medicine to your child.

Breastfeeding mothers may develop thrush on their nipples. If you breastfeed, both you and your child will be treated. This is to prevent passing the infection back and forth. You may be given an ointment to apply to your skin or an oral antifungal medicine.

Talk with your child's healthcare providers about the risks, benefits, and possible side effects of all medicines.

It's also important to boil (sterilize) and disinfect any pacifiers, bottle nipples, or toys that your child may put in their mouth after each use. This will prevent your child from being infected again. Oral thrush is treated with antifungal medication, but you can also ease uncomfortable symptoms with home remedies such as salt water, yogurt, clove oil, apple cider vinegar, and more. Diluted baking soda (sodium bicarbonate) may also combat the symptoms of thrush. Dissolve a half teaspoon of baking soda in 1 cup of warm water, and apply to your child's thrush with a cotton swab. You can also apply the paste on your nipples before breastfeeding (just wipe off before your baby latches). Thrush often goes away on its own in a few days.

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